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Where do the top talent in Taiwan come from and where do they work? A preliminary study of the Yushan Fellow Program

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Introduction

The global competition for talent has intensified in the past two decades due to the increasing demand for highly-skilled labor in the knowledge economy (OECD, 2008). A 2012 report predicted that Taiwan would face the biggest threat of “talent deficit” compared to other countries in the world by 2021 (Oxford Economics, 2012). The impact of talent shortage goes beyond industry and hits higher education as well. During the 11th National Science and Technology Conference, experts concluded that the two main challenges for Taiwan’s higher education were (1) the lack of mobility flows and lack of attractiveness to global talent; and (2) the lower involvement of international collaboration and internationalization among higher education institutions (MOST, 2020).

To combat these persistent challenges, several remedial measures have been implemented by the Ministry of Education (MOE) and the Ministry of Science and Technology (MOST) as part of a long-term plan for national talent development. For instance, in response to the request for cultivating local talent with a global vision, both ministries have initiated funding programs that encourage students and early-career researchers to conduct research stays overseas and, for students, to pursue doctoral degrees. Likewise, similar talent funding programs by both ministries, with slightly different foci, have been introduced to tackle the challenges of talent recruitment and retention due to relatively low salaries and research grants in Taiwan compared to other Asian countries (Huang, 2014). While the Young Scholar Fellowship Program (YSFP), launched by the MOST, aims to provide better research resources and environment, MOE’s Yushan Fellow Program (YFP) focuses on improving salary conditions.

The policy objective of the YFP is “to assist higher education institutions in Taiwan to attract the world’s elite by providing international competitive salaries and benefits so that their expertise can take root in Taiwan’s academic environment and increase the international impact of Taiwan’s higher education.”¹ One important selection criterion for both Yushan Fellows (YF) and Yushan Young Fellows (YYF) is working at a leading international research institution or an internationally renowned company for at least 10 or 5 years, respectively. The emphasis on the international mobility experience implies a positive connection between research impact and international mobility (Sugimoto, Robinson-García, Murray, Yegros-Yegros, Costas & Larivière, 2017; Aksnes, Rørstad, Piro & Sivertsen, 2013).

Since the inception of the YFP, there have been 120 awardees visiting or working in 16 universities in Taiwan. However, neither the program effectiveness nor the characteristics of the Fellows and the schools have been systematically studied. As the first study on the YFP, we focused on the following three research questions:

1. What are the demographic and academic characteristics of the awardees? Are there differences between Yushan Fellows and Young Fellows? Specifically, what are their mobility experiences, and how that might differ by fields of study?
2. What are the institutional characteristics of the schools where they work? How many and what type of Yushan Fellows are there in each school?
3. To what extent does YFP meet its policy objective in increasing the international impact of Taiwan’s higher education?

Our hypothesis is that a national policy like YFP will have an impact on institutions and individuals who are also actors in the national academic field. Nonetheless, the impact is not unidirectional, as the action taken by individual and institutional actors will also determine the extent to which the policy achieve its goal. Although the answer to the three questions may be rudimentary, the ultimate goal of this project is to provide a better evaluation framework for the kind of funding program that is ambitious in its prospect but small-scale in its implementation.

Data and Methods

A list of 120 Yushan (Young) Fellows was downloaded from the program website,² with information on the academic year awarded, name of the awardees, school with which the awardees affiliated in Taiwan, field of study, and type of the award (YF vs. YYF). Additional information was collected manually by examining official/personal web pages, curriculum vitae, press releases, and news reports: gender, email address, ORCID ID, PhD degree (school, country, year), bachelor’s degree (school, country), and most recent work experience (title, institution, country). Institution-level data were gathered from the Department of Statistics, Ministry of Education³ and InCites, Clarivate.

Given the exploratory nature of this study, we conducted exploratory data analysis (Tukey, 1977) to explore possible patterns in the data that might help answer our research questions.

¹ <https://yushan.moe.gov.tw/TopTalent/EN/Intro>

² <https://yushan.moe.gov.tw/TopTalent/Home/Statistics>

³ <https://depart.moe.edu.tw/ED4500/Default.aspx>

Preliminary Findings

Characteristics of Yushan (Young) Fellows

Table 1 provides the summary statistics of demographic and academic characteristics of Yushan (Young) Fellows. Of 120 fellows, only 16.7% are female (n=20), and only three of these are senior fellows. The majority of the fellows work in the fields of Engineering (36.2%) and Natural Sciences (25.2%), followed by Agriculture & Life Sciences (12.6%), Social Sciences (11.7%), and Medical Sciences (9.4%), with Arts & Humanities as the least (4.7%). 70% of Fellows obtained their bachelor's degree in Taiwan, but the percentage is much higher among the YYFs (81.4%) than YF (54%). Most fellows went abroad for their Ph.D. study, with the United States the most popular destination, accounting for 66% of the YFs and 51.4% of the YYFs respectively. However, it is also worth noting that 30% of the YYFs obtained their Ph.D. degree in Taiwan, while none of the YFs did. Another noticeable, if expected, difference is the nearly 30-year gap between the YFs and the YYFs in the mean year of obtaining their Ph.D. degree (1985 vs. 2014). Combining these two facts into consideration, this might reflect the considerable progress of Taiwan's Ph.D. capacity building during the past three decades, especially in the field of Natural Sciences and Medical Sciences, where locally trained YYFs amount to 40% and 80% respectively. In contrast, all the YYFs in Social Sciences obtained their Ph.D. degree in the United States, possibly reflecting the highly U.S.-centered scholarship in this field.

Table 1. Summary statistics of demographic and academic characteristics of Yushan (Young) Fellows.

Variable		YF (n=50)	YYF (n=70)	Total (n=120)
Gender	Women	3 (6.0)	17 (24.3)	20 (16.7)
	Men	47 (94.0)	53 (75.7)	100 (83.3)
Field of Study	Agriculture & Life Sciences	5 (8.8)	11 (15.7)	16 (12.6)
	Arts & Humanities	4 (7.0)	2 (2.9)	6 (4.7)
	Engineering	23 (40.4)	23 (32.9)	46 (36.2)
	Medical Sciences	7 (12.3)	5 (7.1)	12 (9.4)
	Natural Sciences	10 (17.5)	22 (31.4)	32 (25.2)
	Social Sciences	7 (14.0)	7 (10.0)	14 (11.7)
Bachelor Location	Taiwan	27 (54.0)	57 (81.4)	84 (70.0)
	Other	23 (46.0)	13 (18.6)	36 (30.0)
Ph.D. Location	Taiwan	–	21 (30.0)	21 (17.5)
	United States	33 (66.0)	37 (52.9)	70 (58.3)
	Other	17 (34.0)	12 (17.1)	29 (24.2)
Ph.D. Year	Mean (SD)	1985.6 (9.7)	2014.3 (2.9)	2002.3 (15.7)

Mobility flows of individual Fellows

To further understand the mobility experiences of the YFs and YYFs, we plotted their mobility trajectories from places where they obtained their bachelor's degree to places obtaining Ph.D., and to places they worked prior to receiving the fellowship and landing in Taiwan. In addition to what we have briefly described in the previous section, Figure 1 gives us a more granular view of countries from which the fellows come and move between while also highlighting the distinct patterns among the YFs and the YYFs respectively. First, compared to the YYFs, Japanese and French scholars are relatively well-represented among the YFs. Second, compared to the YFs, the places where the YYFs worked after Ph.D. are more scattered, despite the similar

concentrations around North America and Western Europe at the Ph.D. stage. This is consistent with the global trend of newly graduated Ph.D. having a more precarious career (Acker, 2008). Third, a considerable portion of both the YFs and the YYFs have previous work experiences in Hong Kong. A closer look at fellows affiliated with Hong Kong (n=12) reveals that 75% are social scientists. Although motivations of relocating to Taiwan may vary wildly among individual fellows, given the political and social turmoil in Hong Kong in recent years, the fact that one tenth of the Yushan (Young) Fellows previously have affiliations with Hong Kong hints on the importance of academic freedom in scientific research (cf. van Noorden, 2012).

Figure 1. Mobility flows of (A) Yushan Fellows and (B) Yushan Young Fellows.

Recruitment focuses of the universities

Although YFP is open to all universities and colleges in Taiwan to submit applications for the candidates they would like to recruit, there are only 16 schools who have had faculty awarded. Table 2 provides an overview of the institutional characteristics of these schools: about 80% are public, 60% are comprehensive, 80% having less than a thousand faculty members, and only five schools are ranked in the top 500 in Times Higher Education (THE) Ranking.

Table 2. Summary statistics of institutional characteristics of the universities which hired Yushan (Young) Fellows.

Variable	University (n=16)	
Type of ownership	Public	13 (81.3)
	Private	3 (18.8)
Type of universities	Comprehensive	10 (62.5)
	Medical	3 (18.8)
	Technological	3 (18.8)
THE Ranking (2022)	1–200	1 (6.3)
	201–400	4 (25.0)
	601–800	3 (18.8)
	801–1000	1 (6.3)
	1000+	7 (43.8)
# of full-time faculty (Assistant Professor and above)	>2,000	1 (6.3)
	1,001–2,000	2 (12.5)
	501–1,000	9 (56.3)
	<=500	4 (25.0)

Note: Percentages may not be total 100% due to rounding.

The distribution of fellows within the 16 schools is extremely uneven, with the top four school accounting for nearly 75% of all the fellows combined (Figure 2). Not surprisingly, all four are so-called first-tier universities in Taiwan in terms of faculty, student, budgets, and resources, and each has strong STEM programs with slightly different orientations. They also recruit much more YYFs than YFs except one, with YYFs making up 77.1%, 60%, and 59.1% of the total fellows recruited respectively. We suspect that this might reflect the different emphasis of these schools on talent recruitment. On the one hand, since YYFs are usually hired as tenure track faculty, universities hiring more YYFs may consider this a partial solution to the aging faculty population (Chen & Joung, 2019). On the other hand, YFs are often well-established and world-renown scholars who stay in Taiwan for only a fixed term. Universities that target at recruiting YFs are thus more likely to capitalize on the fellows' reputations to increase schools' visibility and expand international collaboration networks.

Figure 2. Number of Yushan (Young) Fellows recruited by university.

Gap in research performance at the institution and country level

The main objective of the YFP is to promote international impact and enhance the research performance of Taiwan's higher education. A common measure for policy evaluation is bibliometric indicators in terms of publication, impact, and international collaboration at the country level. Figure 3 presents a trend analysis of bibliometric indicators including % of international collaborations, % of papers in the top 1% most highly cited, and Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI) for the national average and top four schools in Taiwan. Although we observe an overall growing trend on the national average for all three indicators, there are considerable variations across the four institutions. In short, there is not enough evidence to support or falsify that the overall progress of Taiwan as a whole in research performance has to do with the YFP per se.

Figure 3. Trends in the percentage of international collaboration, the percentage of papers in top 1%, and the value of Category Normalized Citation Impact (CNCI) for the top four schools in Taiwan and the national average (2015–2021).

Source: InCites, Clarivate (April 2022). Document type: article, review.

Discussion, Limitation, and Future Work

While the policy rationale of the YFP is to increase Taiwan's research/scientific impact globally, our preliminary findings suggest goal misalignment between government (MOE), hiring institutions, and individual fellows. Institutions may have different motives when recruiting YFs (gaining national/international reputation and expanding international collaboration networks) and YYFs (replacing retiring faculty). At the same time, individuals who decide to come or return to Taiwan have even more diverse motivations.

As to the program itself, the YFP should be considered more a policy leverage than an instrument. The nature of YFP is an award program, which provides considerable monetary subsidies to awardees to make up for the low salaries Taiwan's college faculty earn on average. In other words, it is an *ad hoc* mechanism and is not going to solve the fundamental issue of low wages in Taiwan. Nonetheless, it has become a good campaign for both universities and government ministries by showing their concern and effort in addressing the problem of talent shortage. Although the direct effect on increasing the international impact of Taiwan's research capacity is unclear, YFP does create a positive image among overseas Taiwanese elites and create strong enough incentives for them to return to Taiwan.

Given its nature as a funding program, we would also like to argue that the YFP needs alternative measures to assess its effectiveness. After all, there are only 120 fellows to date, whereas the number of researchers in Taiwan exceeds 40,000. Therefore, it is unlikely that the YFP will achieve its intended goal in the short run. Instead of citation impact or global university ranking, a potential alternative may be looking at the dynamic change of collaboration networks at the individual, institution, and country level.

Finally, talent development and recruitment need cross-sector collaboration and joint effort from all stakeholders. There is no single funding program that can solve the problem of “brain drain.” The fundamental solution relies on the collaboration and negotiation between ministries to provide competitive salaries, ensure stable supply of research resources, and create better research culture. One possible next step is to examine and analyze how similar funding programs and policies interact with and influence one another.

Although the sample is limited in size with an exclusive focus on Taiwan, the data gathered at both individual and institutional levels should shed some light on institutional and policy-related determinants as well as individual motivations for mobility choice. More importantly, by pointing out the potential goal misalignments between the macro- (government), meso- (institutional), and micro- (individual) level in terms of talent recruitment and mobility decision, we would like to call for more responsible and comprehensive measures to evaluate policy interventions concerning brain-gain/brain-drain.

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